

KOSHI-SHVARTS VA GYOLDER TENGSIZLIKLARI YORDAMIDA BA'ZI OLIMPIADA MASALALARINI YECHISH USULLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Koshi-Shvarts va Gyolder tengsizliklari yordamida ba'zi olimpiada masalalarini yechish usullari keltirilgan. Koshi-Shvarts va Gyolder tengsizliklari matematikada muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, ular ko'plab olimpiada masalalarida qo'llaniladi. Ushbu tengsizliklarning asosiy afzalliklari ularning qamrovli qo'llanilishi va parametr sifatida o'zgartirish kiritish mumkinligi bilan bog'liq.

Kalit so'zlar: Koshi-Shvarts tengsizligi, Gyolder tengsizligi, proporsional sonlar, olimpiada masalalari, musbat haqiqiy sonlar.

Misollar ko'rishdan oldin Koshi-Shvarts va Gyolder tengsizliklari bilan qisqacha tanishib chiqamiz.

Koshi-Shvarts tengsizligi. Har qanday $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ va $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ haqiqiy sonlar uchun quyidagi tengsizlik bajariladi:

$$(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_n^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + \dots + b_n^2) \geq (a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + \dots + a_nb_n)^2.$$

Bu yerda $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ va $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ sonlari proporsional bo'lgan holdagina tenglik

belgisi bajariladi. Ya'ni $\frac{a_1}{b_1} = \frac{a_2}{b_2} = \dots = \frac{a_n}{b_n}$.

Gyolder tengsizligi bu Koshi-Shvarts tengsizligining umumiy lashgan holi bo'lib, u quyidagicha.

Gyolder tengsizligi. Aytaylik $a_i, 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n$ sonlar musbat haqiqiy sonlar bo'lsin. U holda bu sonlar uchun quyidagi tengsizlik bajariladi

$$\prod_{i=1}^m \left(\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} \right) \geq \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \sqrt[m]{\prod_{i=1}^m a_{ij}} \right)^m.$$

Bu tengsizlikni tushunish birmuncha qiyin ko‘ringanligi sababli soddalik maqsadida $a, b, c, p, q, r, x, y, z$ musbat haqiqiy sonlar uchun ohirgi tengsizlikning quyidagi xususiy holini qaraymiz:

$$(a^3 + b^3 + c^3)(p^3 + q^3 + r^3)(x^3 + y^3 + z^3) \geq (aqx + bqy + crz)^3.$$

1-misol. a, b va c haqiqiy sonlar uchun

$$3(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) \geq (a + b + c)^2$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini isbotlang.

Isboti. Demak, Koshi-Shvarts tengsizligiga ko‘ra

$$(1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) \geq (1a + 1b + 1c)^2.$$

2-misol. x, y, z manfiy bo‘lmagan sonlar uchun quyidagi tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini isbotlang:

$$\sqrt{3x^2 + xy} + \sqrt{3y^2 + yz} + \sqrt{3z^2 + zx} \geq 2(x + y + z).$$

Isboti. Koshi-Shvarts tengsizligiga binoan

$$\sqrt{x(3x + y)} + \sqrt{y(3y + z)} + \sqrt{z(3z + x)} = \sqrt{4(x + y + z)^2} = 2(x + y + z).$$

3-misol. Musbat haqiqiy a, b, c sonlar ushun quyidagi tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini isbotlang:

$$\frac{a}{2a + b} + \frac{b}{2b + c} + \frac{c}{2c + a} \geq 1.$$

Isboti. Ma’lumki

$$\frac{a}{2a + b} \geq \frac{1}{3}$$

$$\text{Y} \quad \frac{a}{2a + b} - \frac{1}{3} \geq \frac{3 - 2a - b}{6}$$

$$\text{Y} \quad -\frac{1}{2} \frac{b}{2a + b} \geq -\frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{Y} \quad \frac{b}{2a + b} \leq 1.$$

Demak, Koshi-Shvarts tengsizligini qo‘llash natijasida biz quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz

$$\sum_{cyc} \frac{b}{2a+b} = \frac{b^2}{2ab+b^2} + \frac{c^2}{2bc+c^2} + \frac{a^2}{2ca+a^2} \geq \frac{(a+b+c)^2}{2(ab+bc+ca)+b^2+c^2+a^2} = 1.$$

4-misol. x, y, z musbat haqiqiy sonlar uchun quyidagi

$$\frac{y^2+z^2}{x} + \frac{z^2+x^2}{y} + \frac{x^2+y^2}{z} \geq 2(x+y+z).$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini isbotlang.

Isboti.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{y^2+z^2}{x} + \frac{z^2+x^2}{y} + \frac{x^2+y^2}{z} &= \left(\frac{y^2}{x} + \frac{z^2}{y} + \frac{x^2}{z} \right) + \left(\frac{z^2}{x} + \frac{x^2}{y} + \frac{y^2}{z} \right) \\ &\geq \frac{(y+z+x)^2}{x+y+z} + \frac{(z+x+y)^2}{x+y+z} = 2(x+y+z). \end{aligned}$$

5-misol. Barcha musbat haqiqiy a, b va c sonlar uchun

$$\frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2+8bc}} + \frac{b}{\sqrt{b^2+8ca}} + \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2+8ab}} \geq 1$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini isbotlang.

Isboti. Gyolder tengsizligiga ko‘ra ushbu

$$\left(\sum_{cyc} \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2+8bc}} \right)^2 \left(\sum_{cyc} a(a^2+8bc) \right) \geq (a+b+c)^3$$

tengsizlik bajariladi. Shuning uchun $(a+b+c)^3 \geq a^3+b^3+c^3+24abc$ tengsizlik bajarilishini ko‘rsatishimiz kifoya. Bizga ma’lum bu tengsizlik barcha musbat haqiqiy sonlar uchun bajariladi.

6-misol. Aytaylik $p \geq 2$ haqiqiy son bo‘lsin. U holda barcha manfiy bo‘lmagan haqiqiy a, b, c sonlar uchun

$$\sqrt[3]{\frac{a^3+pabc}{1+p}} + \sqrt[3]{\frac{b^3+pabc}{1+p}} + \sqrt[3]{\frac{c^3+pabc}{1+p}} \leq a+b+c$$

tengsizlik bajarilishini isbotlang.

Isbot. Demak, Gyolder tengsizligi bo‘yicha

$$\left(\sum_{cyc} \sqrt[3]{\frac{a^3 + pabc}{1+p}} \right)^3 = \left(\sum_{cyc} \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{1+p} \cdot a \cdot (a^2 + pbc)} \right)^3 \leq \left(\sum_{cyc} \frac{1}{1+p} \right) \left(\sum_{cyc} a \right) \left(\sum_{cyc} a^2 + pbc \right).$$

Bu yerda $a^2 + b^2 + c^2 \geq ab + bc + ca$ bo'lganligi uchun

$$\sum_{cyc} a^2 + pbc \leq (p+1) \sum_{cyc} \frac{a^2 + 2bc}{3} = \frac{p+1}{3} (a+b+c)^2$$

tengsizlikni olamiz. Demak, so'ngi tengsizlikdan

$$\left(\sum_{cyc} \sqrt[3]{\frac{a^3 + pabc}{1+p}} \right)^3 \leq \frac{3}{p+1} \cdot (a+b+c) \cdot \frac{p+1}{3} (a+b+c)^2 = (a+b+c)^3$$

isbotlanishi talab etilgan tengsizlikni olamiz.

ADABIYOTLAR

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